

Some trace elements enhance biosorption of lead by *Rhizopus arrhizus*

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A high concentration of lead adapted strain of *Rhizopus arrhizus* was found to be efficient for lead biosorption from culture medium containing 1 mg dm^{-3} of lead when the physiological conditions and the chemical composition of the medium were optimized. In the present study, effect of some other trace metals, e.g. iron and manganese, on the biosorption of lead by the microorganism is deciphered when present with lead in the culture medium. It has been found that when iron and manganese in their +2 state are supplemented in the culture medium individually or in combination, biosorption of lead increased from 70.15 to 74.72% in the culture medium containing 1 mg dm^{-3} lead. It has also been found that the tolerance of the microorganism towards lead also increased.

Rapid industrialization and increasing domestic activities have led to an increase in the biogeochemical cycling of several heavy metals. Developing countries are increasingly concerned with pollution due to discharge and recycling of toxic heavy metals in the natural water systems, as the source of these pollutants is mainly the agricultural run-offs, industrial and domestic effluents and acid mine drainage¹. Among toxic heavy metals, lead is one which mainly accumulates in the skeleton when taken with the food-stuff. There are several physical and chemical methods available which is employed in the bioremediation of lead viz., chemical precipitation, chemical oxidation and reduction, filtration, electrochemical treatments and application of membrane technology². But these processes are ineffective and extremely expensive when metal concentration in the solutions ranges between $1\text{--}100 \text{ mg dm}^{-3}$ ³. In the light of this context, low-cost and eco-friendly processes, with the help of microbial technologies, were developed which must ease metal absorption and recovery⁴.

Rhizopus arrhizus, dead or alive, was used extensively by different workers to remove heavy metals from solutions⁵ due to its ease of culturing and lack of pathogenicity to human or other animals. A lead adapted strain of the microorganism, *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1, has been isolated in our laboratory which absorbed more lead than other heavy metals⁶. The efficiency of the adapted strain has been increased if optimal physiological conditions and chemical composition of the culture medium was used. The present study deciphered the effect of iron and manganese in their +2 state on the biosorption capacity of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 in the light of possible environmental application for

bioremediation of lead from water solutions.

Results and discussion

A variant of the mold, *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1, has been reported to remove lead in much higher quantity from synthetic growth medium containing lead⁶. It has also been observed that lead biosorption is greater than other metals when metals like cadmium, chromium and nickel were used in single experiments using only one metal at a time. It was found that iron and manganese in their +2 state enhances biosorption of lead by the microorganism. Fig. 1 showed that when iron or manganese is added to the synthetic growth medium separately, biosorption of lead increased from the control, although the extent of increase is not very sharp. 15 mg dm^{-3} of iron in the medium showed maximum biosorption of lead among different concentrations of iron and 5 mg dm^{-3} of manganese in the medium showed maximum biosorption among different concentrations of manganese. That iron in the +2 state is essential for many fungi has been confirmed in a number of studies⁷. Actually, its association with a number of enzymes supports the role of iron in fungal growth. This has also been supported by the present observations. It is also evident from Fig. 1 that biosorption is more at a higher concentration of iron than manganese, [72.86% with 15 mg dm^{-3} of iron than 71.05% with 5 mg dm^{-3} of manganese]. This may be due to the fact that iron is more essential than manganese for biological systems.

Fig. 1 also illustrated the effect of both the metals on biosorption of lead when supplemented in combination with different concentrations. It can be seen from the above fig-

Fig. 1. Effect of lead biosorption at different concentrations of iron (+2) and manganese (+2). In all experiments, initial lead concentration was 1 mg dm^{-3} and initial pH of the medium was 4.5.

ure that biosorption of lead increased at a lower concentration of both the metals [5 mg dm^{-3} of iron and 1 mg dm^{-3} of manganese in combination]. When individual optimum concentrations of the two metals [15 mg dm^{-3} of iron and 5 mg dm^{-3} of manganese] were added simultaneously in the synthetic growth medium, biosorption of lead decreased considerably. This may be due to the increased competition of lead for the metal binding sites on the cell surface of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 with iron and manganese ions.

Table 1 showed the tolerability of the adapt strain *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 towards higher concentration of lead in presence of iron and manganese ions. When there was no trace metals present in the synthetic growth medium, maximum biosorption was achieved at an initial lead concentration of 1 mg dm^{-3} . Lead biosorption gradually decreased with increased lead concentrations. This was also observed with the parent strain of *Rhizopus arrhizus*⁶. In case of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1, biosorption capacity increased considerably with supplementation of optimum concentrations of both iron and manganese in combination which was also

Table 1. Increase of biosorption capacity of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 from medium containing different concentrations of lead with the supplementation of iron and manganese at optimum concentrations

Initial pH of the medium was 4.5

Concn. of lead (mg dm^{-3})	Concn. of iron (mg dm^{-3})	Concn. of manganese (mg dm^{-3})	Biosorption of lead (%) (Mean \pm SE)	Final pH of the medium (Mean \pm SE)
0	0	0	00.00	3.0 (\pm 0.08)
0.5	0	0	66.25 (\pm 0.72)	2.9 (\pm 0.06)
0.5	5	1	69.83 (\pm 0.66)	2.5 (\pm 0.14)
1.0	0	0	70.15 (\pm 0.13)	2.8 (\pm 0.08)
1.0	5	1	74.72 (\pm 0.42)	2.4 (\pm 0.14)
1.5	0	0	69.37 (\pm 0.29)	2.8 (\pm 0.13)
1.5	5	1	72.86 (\pm 0.44)	2.3 (\pm 0.09)
2.0	0	0	66.82 (\pm 0.51)	2.6 (\pm 0.12)
2.0	5	1	70.07 (\pm 0.21)	2.1 (\pm 0.11)
3.0	0	0	61.73 (\pm 0.48)	2.9 (\pm 0.04)
3.0	5	1	68.25 (\pm 0.31)	2.2 (\pm 0.13)
4.0	0	0	52.28 (\pm 0.76)	3.0 (\pm 0.16)
4.0	5	1	65.39 (\pm 0.18)	2.4 (\pm 0.09)
5.0	0	0	44.08 (\pm 0.62)	3.3 (\pm 0.12)
5.0	5	1	60.95 (\pm 0.28)	2.6 (\pm 0.08)

*n = 4

illustrated in Table 1. Increased tolerance of the adapted strain towards lead might be due to superior metabolic activity of the microorganism in presence of the two minerals as they might increase enzymatic activities.

Experimental

All the chemicals used were of A.R. grade (E. Merck) and the media preparation and volume make up were done by double-distilled water.

Rhizopus arrhizus M1, a high concentration of lead tolerant strain⁶ was used in this study. The microorganism was maintained in potato-dextrose agar slants at 4°C .

Spore suspension for the studies was prepared as described elsewhere⁹. 5 days old culture of *Rhizopus arrhizus* M1 was used for the preparation of the spore suspension. The count of the spores in the suspension was adjusted to 4.5×10^7 spores/ml in all the studies.

Composition of synthetic culture medium for metal uptake experiments was (as g/100 ml) : sucrose, 5; NH_4NO_3 , 0.2; K_2HPO_4 , 0.2; $\text{MgSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$, 0.05. pH of the medium was adjusted to 4.5. A Systronic digital pH meter (Model 335) was used for pH measurements. Stock solutions of $\text{Pb}(\text{NO}_3)_2$, $\text{FeSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ and $\text{MnSO}_4 \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ having concentrations of 1000 mg dm^{-3} with respect to the metals were

prepared separately. Calculated volumes of these stock solutions were added to the synthetic culture media to achieve desired metal concentrations. 50 ml synthetic growth medium was taken in 250 ml Erlenmeyer flasks containing desired metal concentrations for individual experiments. Freshly prepared spore suspension was added and the medium was incubated at 28° for 7 days. All the experiments were done in quadruplicate sets, mean of the four values was taken for calculation and standard error was also determined. Statistical analysis was carried out using student's *t*-test. A level of significance of $P < 0.001$ was recorded for all samples which was regarded as statistically significant.

After desired period of incubation, the cell mass was separated and the lead content was analyzed for individual sets by Atomic Absorption Spectrometry as described elsewhere⁶.

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